

Feminism in India : Impact of Feminism on Indian Society

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Abstract

For centuries, feminism has been a widely discussed subject across the globe. It means granting the same rights to women as those enjoyed by men . It does not only talk of equality and rights of women but it is more about compassion, respect and understanding from the male counterparts. In post-independence India where education had already commenced the New Woman has also begun to emerge . Education has inculcated a sense of individuality among women and has aroused an interest in their human rights. However, women throughout the world have faced different types of challenges and hurdles in their lives, at some stage of their lives. They are still in need of due recognition in various fields they work. In a country like India with its deep-rooted tradition and culture women play a pivot role in the development of the society. The idea behind writing this research paper is to study the nature of Indian society which is a root cause of pitiable condition of women in India. It focuses on why feminism is so crucial in a country like India and also what changes it has brought in the lives of Indian women. Though it faces much troubles yet it has been able to succeed to improve the condition of Indian women.

Key words: Feminism, India & Indian Society.

Introduction

Feminism, a word which is very commonly used among the people in their daily conversations debates and discussions. But at the same time, it is the most misapprehended and the most misused word, too. What does the word feminism imply? Is it a war against men or is it an attempt to prove women's supremacy over men or is it a struggle for women's rights. Feminism, actually, refers to a mode of thought that is concerned with the condition of women in society. It is the notion that denotes that all humans are equal regardless of the gender. Its focus is on the causes of women's sufferings, deprivations and upliftment of women so that men and women are treated equally. It is not about demeaning men or declaring them inferior. It is not based on women having power over men rather the idea is that women should have power over themselves . Its focus is on emancipation of women so that they can restore their due position and be treated equally with men with a fair share in prestige , power , wealth and rights. It focuses on subjection of women and the injustice being done against women which is the result of years of patriarchy and toxic masculinity. It is an attempt to get rid of this notion of subordination and dominance to bring both genders at equal level.

What Is Feminism

Feminism is a range of Socio-Political movements and ideologies that aim to define and establish the political economic personal and social equality of the sexes. It incorporates the position that society prioritizes the male point of view and that women are treated unjustly in these societies. Efforts to change this include fighting against gender stereotypes and establishing educational , professional and interpersonal opportunities and outcomes for women that are equal to those for men.

Feminist movements have campaigned and continue to campaign for women's rights including the right to vote, run for public office, work, earn equal pay, own property, receive education, enter contracts, have equal rights within marriage and maternity leave. Feminists have also worked to ensure access to contraception legal abortions, social integration and to protect women and girls from rape, sexual harassment and domestic violence. Changes in female dress standards and acceptable physical activities for females have often been part of feminist movements.

Although feminist advocacy is and has been mainly focused on women's rights some feminists argue for the inclusion of men's liberation within its aims because they believe that men are also harmed by traditional gender roles.

Numerous feminist movements and ideologies have developed over the years and represent different viewpoints and aims. Traditionally since the 19th century, first wave liberal feminism that sought political and legal equality through reforms within a liberal democratic framework was contrasted with labour based proletarian women's movements that over time developed into Socialist and Marxist feminism based on class struggle theory . Since the 1960s both of these traditions are also contrasted with radical feminism that arose from the radical wing of second wave feminism and that calls for a radical reordering of society to eliminate male supremacy . Together liberal, socialist and radical feminisms are sometimes called the 'Big Three' schools of feminist thought. Since the 20th century many newer forms of feminisms have emerged . Some forms of feminism have been criticized for taking into account only white, middle class, college educated and heterosexual perspectives. These criticisms have led to the creation of multicultural forms of feminism such as black feminism and intersectional feminism . Some feminists have argued that feminism often promotes elevation of women's interest above men's and criticize radical feminist positions as harmful to both men and women

Feminism in India

Women in India are raised in a different social and cultural setup . Indian society is considered as a conservative and closed system with its orthodox views . There is more focus on the emancipation of women to a greater extent . There is always an inner urge in women to come out of the clutches of the patriarchal society which is deep rooted in India

Even before the term feminism was introduced in India, we had some great feminist icons in our culture and history e.g., Draupadi, Durga maa, Sita , Rani Laxmibai and Chand Bibi etc. All these are the examples of immense courage and power Draupadi, a woman born out of fire avenged the humiliation meted out to her in the Mahabharat . Durga maa, an incarnation of Goddess Parvati was created as an amalgamation of all the Gods to destroy evil. In the Ramayana Sita fought for her Independence and raised her two sons single handedly. Rani Laxmibai and Chand Bibi are other examples of power and courage

Women of the past from the mythologies to the women of the modern era are engulfed by posterity . But, now time is changing in India where women enjoy the dual role of a house maker and a working woman. They are traditional as mothers, wives, sisters and daughters balancing the cultural expectation at the same time not losing their individual self. Today women shine in various fields as business entrepreneurs, professionals, scientists, politicians, actors etc and also end up as housemaids or helpers but whatever be their job, they are financially independent and secure thus redefining their roles in an ever-changing versatile scenario.

According to history feminism in India is divided into three phases :-

1. It was initiated in the beginning of the mid 18th century when European men began to speak against woman self-immolation known as 'Sati'
2. Then another phase started after 1915 till independence of India, when Gandhiji incorporated women's movements into the Quit India Movement and independent women's organisations began to emerge.
3. And third phase after independence which focused on fair treatment of women at home after marriage.

Why feminism is needed in a country like India?

India ranks very poorly in all sorts and parameters of gender indices. Talk about gender inequality, sex ratio, the gap on pay scales, percentage of the work force and we have painted a very grim picture out of these. Gender disparity and discriminatory social setup is too wide and the voices to bridge the gap is too few. Like their feminist counterparts all over the world feminists in India seek gender equality, right to work for equal wages, right to equal access to health and education and equal political rights. Feminism in India is the pursuit of women's rights within the society of India. In general, feminism can be seen as a movement to put an end to sexism, sexist exploitation and oppression and to achieve full gender equality in law and in practice.

Reasons why feminism is so crucial in India-

To promote gender equality

In many Indian families males and females are treated differently. Boys have all access to the best education and nutrition while the girls have been denied these and been neglected. Women in many Indian families eat last after serving all the other family members. In Indian society a girl is treated as a burden as marriage is considered to be the only reason for her existence. Even today, every year thousands of women die due to dowry harassment and a number of girls are killed in their mother's womb.

To rid women from male dominance

There is a strong belief that women are not designed to protect but to be protected. There is a need to break such belief. A woman should not be treated as a responsibility of a male throughout her life whether it be her father, brother, husband or son.

To end the stereotyped gender roles

Even professions and family roles have been stereotyped based on gender. e.g., some professions like engineering, aviation and military are considered masculine and professions like teaching, fashion designing and home making are considered feminine. Stereotyping in family includes how men are expected to be the whole bread winners and females are presumed to single handily take up the responsibilities of managing home.

To ensure that women are respected regardless of their career choices-

A certain section of our society believes that it is an offence if a woman is well educated and working to support herself or her family financially. Another section of our society believes that becoming a housewife would contribute little to women's empowerment.

To end the idea that men need to be physically and emotionally stronger than women.

To stop telling women how to dress.

Often girls are criticized for their choice of clothing. There are several instances where fatwas have been issued against female celebrities for wearing western clothes. Another such appalling incident occurred where a prominent politician compared immodest clothes with an invitation to rape. Mindless WhatsApp forwards and serials and movies that normalise stalking and eve teasing worsen situation.

Impact of feminism on Indian society-

The impact of feminism has led to a set of movements aimed at defining, establishing and defending equal political, economic and social rights and opportunities for women in India. It is the pursuit of women's rights within the society of India.

From 1970 onwards development of social movements highlighting the problems of rural and urban poor, industrial working class, tribal masses and minorities threw up new kind of women decision makers who had the combined strength of street fighting, formal education and strategic thinking. In

90s other sectors of society also gave space to competent and highly qualified women to be in decision making bodies.

Feminist movements in India have posed challenges to established patriarchal Institutions such as family, dominant social values and legal structures particularly with regard to violence against women. Women's movements in India raised diverse issues e.g. land rights, wages, employment, security at workplace, water availability, destruction of nature, oppression and exploitation of dalits and the working masses. Many women participated in these struggles with enthusiasm, responsibility and credibility.

The major goals of the feminist movements include creating equal opportunities and new freedoms for women. The purpose of the feminist movement has shifted overtime. Today gender bias continues to create huge barriers for many women. Ongoing struggles include ensuring equal economic opportunities, educational equality and an end to gender-based violence.

In modern India feminist demands have led to several appeals in the form of conventions :-

- Convention against Discrimination of Women
- Convention on combating the crimes of trafficking in women and children etc.

In other issues such as dowry deaths, custodial rape feminists have focused on specific roles and factors that patriarchy play in the perpetration of these gender-based crimes.

At present we have several women's organisations which may be separated by political ideology, however, often come together and show unity while viewing their concerns about violence against women. These include :-

National Federation of Indian Women (NFIW)

- All India Democratic Women's Association (AIDWA)
- Mahila Dakshita Samiti (MDS)
- All India Women's Conference (AIWC)
- Young Women's Christian Association (YWCA)
- Joint Women's Program (JWP)
- Centre for Women's Development Studies (CWDS)

They are also popularly referred to as 'Seven Sisters'

The Indian constitution granted equality, freedom from discrimination based on gender or religion and guaranteed religious freedom. Earlier women in India were facing challenges like child marriages, sati pratha, devadasi pratha, restriction on widow remarriage, widow exploitation etc. However, all such old practices have almost vanished but that doesn't mean an end to the challenges women face. Still today women and young girls everywhere face an immense range of challenges from the inability to access food, education and employment to the threat of gender-based violence.

Gender equitable societies are healthy for everyone. As feminism challenges restrictive gender norms, improvement in women's access to health care, reproductive rights and protection from violence have positive effects on everyone life expectancy and well being especially children. The greatest impact of feminism on Indian society is women empowerment. With higher literacy rates and equal pay for equal work, women are able to thrive economically and rise out of poverty. Protecting girls and women from violence and abuse while challenging the stigmas against reporting crimes would overall create a much safer society.

The positive side of the impact of feminism is that it has created a sense of collectiveness rather than individuality. Moreover, it has increased the importance of motherhood, too. But at the same time, it has been criticized for having too much western influence and posing too much focus on upper class women's needs and ignoring lower classes generally.

Conclusion:-

It is time to recognise that feminism is not about making women strong. Women are already strong. It's about changing the way the world perceives the strength. Nobody should be afraid of being referred

to as a feminist because it frees both men and women from the imposed gender stereotypes . Feminism should not be perceived as hostility against men because me asking for my rights will not deprive you of yours . True feminism i.e., feminism that seeks to liberate all women leads inexorably to solidarity politics , solidarity economics and revolution , a global citizens movement as described by the Great Transition initiative.

Feminism has proved itself instrumental to society through a variety of measures . Through this movement voting rights was secured for women , as was greater access to education and an increased level of bodily autonomy . Recent movements such as '**Me Too**' brought the conversation about sexual harassment and assault to the mainstream serving as a wakeup call for not only the entertainment industry but other industries worldwide . This in turn led to tangible reformations in many workplaces in the form of social and policy change . Expanded attention on intersectional feminism , in addition , has increased the inclusivity of the movement taking into account religion , sexuality and caste .Feminism is thus a vitally important movement as it promotes the equality and well being of all people throughout every aspect of society.

In conclusion, we still need feminism in our society much has been achieved and women today enjoy many more rights that they did only a few decades ago but so much still remains to be done. It is about time or way past time that people come up and speak against the conventional and orthodox social order which is inhumanly discriminatory at its core against something as natural as sexes.

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